

Mapping the Mind of OpenAlex: Evaluating Neuroscience Indexing in an Open Scholarly Ecosystem - Group 5 Project Report

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Table of Contents

1. Introduction	4
2. Literature	
Review	4
2.1 Background on Knowledge Organization Systems (KOSs).....	5
2.2 OpenAlex.....	5
2.3 Comparative Insights.....	6
I. Inclusion and Coverage.....	7
II. Research Evaluation and Citation Performance.....	7
III. Technical Infrastructure and Interoperability.....	7
2.4 Conclusion of Literature Review.....	7
3. Evaluation of the Classification System	8
3.1 Quantitative Evaluation.....	8
3.2 Qualitative Evaluation.....	11
3.3 Evaluation of Indexing.....	13
I. Subfields.....	13
II. Topics.....	18
4. Recommendations	23
4.1 Expand Underrepresented Subfields to Increase Conceptual Coverage.....	23
4.2 Enhance Granularity in High-density Subfields	24
4.3 Integrate External Knowledge Organization Systems.....	24
4.4 Standardize Topic Definitions and Mapping Rules	24
4.5 Rebalance Topic Assignment	25
5. Conclusion	25
6. Bibliography	26

List of Figures and Tables

Figure 1. Pie chart illustrating the number of topic samples within each neuroscience subfield.....	9
Figure 2. Line chart displaying the distribution of distinct topics across neuroscience subfields.....	10
Figure 3. Bar graph depicting the total works count associated with each topic.....	11
Figure 4. SankeyMATIC diagram showing the flow of topics into their assigned subfields.....	12

Figure 5. Comparison of OpenAlex and MeSH hierarchies.....	16
Table 1. Manual indexing results by subfield, including justification for classification..... quality and indicators contributing to accuracy gaps	13
Figure 6. Proposed restructuring of existing subfields (Model A).....	15
Figure 7. Proposed restructuring of existing subfields (Model B).....	18
Figure 8. Double bar graph comparing pre- and post-reconciliation manual indexing..... outcomes across subfields, highlighting variations in classification accuracy and patterns of topic misassignment	19
Table 2. Manual indexing results for the topic Neuroscience and..... Neuropharmacology Research, including justification	20
Figure 9. Proposed restructuring of existing topic and article (Model C).....	22

1.Introduction

Open access scholarly tools play a critical role in supporting inclusive, comprehensive, and transparent research discovery. Among these systems, OpenAlex has emerged as a prominent open-access knowledge graph, offering large-scale, structured metadata that links research works to journals, authors, institutions, concepts, citations, and funding sources. While the platform provides an important alternative to proprietary bibliometric databases, its current metadata infrastructure, particularly in topic and subfield classification, exhibits notable inconsistencies. Because citation indexes shape how scholars navigate, interpret, and evaluate research landscapes, assessing the reliability of OpenAlex’s classification system is essential for understanding its strengths and limitations as a discovery tool.

This study undertakes a systematic evaluation of OpenAlex’s topic assignments within the field of neuroscience using a mixed-methods design. A randomized sample of topics was analyzed using descriptive statistical measures to quantify patterns in subfield distribution, followed by qualitative assessment to examine the clarity, coherence, and appropriateness of topic-subfield relationships. These findings are supported through visualizations, including graphs, charts, Sankey diagrams, and table results, to illustrate structural irregularities and classification discrepancies.

By examining both the numerical patterns and the interpretive dimensions of topic assignment, this study provides a clearer understanding of how OpenAlex organizes neuroscience research. The analysis aims to inform researchers, institutions, and platform developers by identifying areas where the classification system functions effectively, where it demonstrates structural imbalance, and where targeted improvements could enhance the accuracy, coverage, and overall utility of OpenAlex as an open scholarly indexing resource.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Background on Knowledge Organization Systems (KOSs)

Knowledge Organization Systems (KOSs) and classification schemes have long been central to organizing, retrieving, and navigating information. Initially developed to structure knowledge systematically, these systems aimed to enhance information access and advance science and human progress (Rafferty, 2001). Early systems, such as the Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC) and Library of Congress Classification (LCC), were largely enumerative, arranging subjects hierarchically into classes and subclasses to facilitate browsing and targeted retrieval (Shiri, 2006; Krishnamurthy, et al., 2023). While practical, these models were rigid and limited in accommodating interdisciplinary or emerging domains (Rafferty, 2001).

Faceted classification systems offer greater flexibility, with Ranganathan's Colon Classification (CC) introducing a bottom-up approach in which semantic categories, or facets, could be combined to represent a work's aboutness more precisely (Krishnamurthy, et al., 2023). Controlled vocabularies, thesauri, and subject headings, including Canadian Subject Headings (CSH), the Art & Architecture Thesaurus (ATT) and Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH) were developed a standardized terminology, reduce ambiguity, and improved discoverability across collections (Shiri, 2006; Hodge, 2000).

The shift from traditional classification systems to digital bibliometric databases was driven by the internet and digital libraries. Canadian institutions, such as Canadian Initiative on Digital Libraries (CIDL) and Library and Archives Canada, have leveraged KOSs to enhance resource discovery through controlled vocabulary searches, hierarchical browsing, and intuitive navigation (Shiri, 2006). Despite widespread adoption, challenges remain in interface design, bilingual support, and interoperability, underscoring the continued relevance of structured knowledge organization in digital environments.

In scholarly research, bibliometric databases such as Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus serve as foundational tools for structured access to research outputs, supporting discovery, evaluation, and citation analysis (Scheidsteger & Haunschild, 2022; Haupka et al., 2024). Despite their influence and long-standing use, these proprietary platforms present several limitations. Access is restricted by paywalls, coverage of non-English publications is uneven, and availability is limited for researchers and institutions without subscription resources (Jiangbo et al., 2025). These constraints underscore the need for robust, open-access alternatives capable of offering broader, more equitable representation of global research.

2.2 OpenAlex

OpenAlex, launched in 2022 as the successor of the Microsoft Academic Graph (MAG), is a fully open, community-driven scholarly knowledge graph that maps the global research ecosystem (Priem et al., 2022). It organizes scholarly outputs, including journal articles, books, datasets, and theses, and links them to the model's 5 entity types: works, authors, venues, institutions, and concepts using persistent identifiers. Concepts are hierarchically structured to represent research topics and disciplines, while citations and other connections create a dynamic network reflecting global research activity (Priem et al., 2022). A key feature of OpenAlex is its topic classification system, which assigns each work to hierarchical research topics, allowing users to explore research trends, disciplinary structures, and knowledge relationships (Barett & Lockspeiser, 2025). Topics are organized into four levels:

1. **Domain:** broad areas of knowledge (e.g., *Life Sciences*).
2. **Field:** sub-disciplines within a domain (e.g., *Neuroscience*).
3. **Subfield:** more specific areas within a field (e.g., *Cognitive Neuroscience*).
4. **Topic:** highly detailed labels applied to individual works (e.g., *Neuroscience and Music Perception*).

This hierarchical system provides precise, paper level classification, making it easier to analyze trends and relationships in research. The system uses information from titles, abstracts, journals, and citations to assign topics, ensuring coverage across disciplines and regions (Barett & Lockspeiser, 2025). Though relatively new, OpenAlex has become a focal point of comparative research against proprietary databases (Wos, Scopus), highlighting both its advantages and limitations (Thelwall et al., 2025). Recent scholarship positions OpenAlex as a strong open access alternative to these bibliometric platforms. The next section synthesizes literature evaluating OpenAlex, focusing on common themes across studies: coverage and inclusivity, research evaluation and citation performance, and technical infrastructure and interoperability, alongside challenges related to metadata depth and document-type accuracy.

2.3 Comparative Insights

I. Inclusion and Coverage

OpenAlex preserves nearly all MAG records while adding over one million new works, significantly expanding its bibliometric coverage (Scheidsteger & Haunschild, 2022; Haupka et al., 2024). OpenAlex has strengthened its document-type classification, particularly for journal articles and book chapters, and expanded coverage across top-level fields of study (FoS), increasing from 74.6% in MAG to 86.6% and improving cross-field comparability. Despite these gains, deeper subfield classifications remain limited, and certain document types, such as conference proceedings and editorial, remain underrepresented (~0.3%) compared to proprietary databases like WoS and Scopus (10-12%). This underrepresentation reflects OpenAlex's reliance on automated metadata collection from Crossref and may introduce bias in analyses that depend on complete document-type distributions.

OpenAlex demonstrates strong open access (OA) coverage and broad inclusivity. By leveraging persistent identifiers such as DOI, ORCID, and ROR, it captures non-English publications, research in the Social Sciences and Humanities, and work from the Global South, while indexing more diamond and gold OA journals to enhance linguistic and regional representation (Forchino & Torres Salinas, 2025). Between 2004 and 2023, OpenAlex's coverage of OA books rising by ~20% compared to 5% in WoS (Jiangbo et al., 2025). OpenAlex also shows broader disciplinary representation in Social Sciences, Computer Science, Environmental Science, and Medicine, while WoS remains dominant in Arts & Humanities and Health Professions.

Another key strength of OpenAlex is its global inclusivity. Alonso-Álvarez & van Eck (2025) report that OpenAlex indexed nearly three times more African publications from 1996 to 2022 than Scopus and WoS, while capturing 97-98% of publications included in other databases and adding unique works not found elsewhere. Metadata quality is generally high for DOIs, titles, authors, and publication years, though references, affiliations, and funding information are less complete, particularly for OpenAlex exclusive records. These findings underscore

OpenAlex's ability to support open access growth, increase visibility for emerging research areas, and enhance global equity and scholarly communication.

II. Research Evaluation and Citation Performance

OpenAlex performs comparably, and in some areas better, than proprietary databases for research evaluation. Thelwall & Jiang (2025) analyzed ~28.7 million articles (2014-2020), including thousands of submissions to the UK Research Excellence Framework (REF) 2021, finding that OpenAlex citation counts exceed Scopus for roughly three-quarters of REF articles and aligned more closely with REF quality assessments. Broad disciplinary domains, such as Life Sciences and Social Sciences, showed the highest correlation with research quality, while finer subfield classifications were less predictive. Raw citation counts (total citations per article) were most effective for within-year comparisons, whereas normalized scores (adjusted for field and year differences) better captured multi-year trends and field variations (Thelwall & Jiang, 2025). These results indicate that OpenAlex is a reliable tool for citation-based evaluation, particularly when using broad classifications and focusing on journal articles.

III. Technical Infrastructure and Interoperability

OpenAlex's technical infrastructure is built around an open, CC0-licensed knowledge graph that integrates metadata from major sources such as Crossref, DataCite, PubMed, HAL, arXiv, and institutional repositories, continuously updating as new research becomes available (Priem et al, 2022). Its technical infrastructures and interoperability are key to its utility and open bibliometrics. Its open, fast, and freely accessible API allows large-scale retrieval of scholarly metadata, which is structured across works, authors, venues, institutions, and concepts, enabling seamless integration with external tools and databases (Forchino & Torres Salinas, 2025). The platforms compatibility with open-source analytics tools such as R and Python, support bibliometric mapping, trend analysis, and network visualization, while persistent identifiers and Canonical External ID's enhanced interoperability across systems and institutional projects (Velez-Estevez et al., 2023). By combining open access, reproducibility, inflexible data structures, OpenAlex facilitates transparent and equitable research analyses, particularly benefiting underrepresented regions and disciplines (Forchino & Torres Salinas, 2025; Jiangbo et al., 2025). Nonetheless, some limitations persist, including incomplete institutional affiliation data, document-type classification, and advanced metric queries, which often require complementary sources.

2.3 Closing Remarks on Literature

The evolution from classical classification systems to modern bibliometric and open access knowledge graphs highlights the enduring importance of structured knowledge organization. These systems continue to support discovery, evaluation, and research transparency for both users and institutions navigating complex digital information landscapes. The literature positions OpenAlex as a robust and increasingly reliable open access alternative to proprietary

bibliometric databases, offering broad and inclusive coverage, strong support for open access publications, alignment with global research outputs, and effective citation-based evaluation. While challenges remain, particularly regarding metadata completeness, document-type classification, and advanced metrics, its open infrastructure, interoperability, and accessibility make it a valuable tool for transparent, equitable, and reproducible bibliometric research. As it develops further, OpenAlex has significant potential to advance open science, support diverse research communities, and complement traditional commercial databases.

3. Evaluation of the Classification System

This section presents a comprehensive assessment of the classification system through three complementary components: (3.1) quantitative evaluation, (3.2) qualitative evaluation, and (3.3) manual indexing evaluation. The quantitative evaluation examines numerical patterns in the distribution of topic samples, topic counts, and works across neuroscience subfields, providing a detailed statistical overview of how research output is allocated. Building on this, the qualitative evaluation analyzes structural characteristics of the classification system, identifying patterns such as subfield imbalance, uneven topic representation, and potential sources of indexing inconsistency. Finally, the manual indexing evaluation assesses the accuracy of topic-to-subfield assignments by comparing system-generated classifications with human-coded judgments. Together, these three sub-sections offer a multilayered analysis of classification performance, highlighting both measurable discrepancies and conceptual alignment issues within the system.

3.1 Quantitative Evaluation

To examine the distribution of topics and research output across neuroscience subfields in OpenAlex, the number of topic samples assigned to each subfield was analyzed. Across a total of 935 topic samples, *Cognitive Neuroscience* contains 364 samples, representing approximately 38.9% of the dataset, while *Cellular and Molecular Neuroscience* includes 313 samples, accounting for 33.5%. Other subfields are considerably less represented: *Neurology* comprises 116 samples (12.4%), *Endocrine and Autonomic Systems* 48 samples (5.1%), *Sensory Systems* 35 samples (3.7%), *Behavioral Neuroscience* 25 samples (2.7%), *Developmental Neuroscience* 25 samples (2.7%), and *Biological Psychiatry* only 9 samples (1%). These figures indicate substantial numeric differences in topic sample allocation across subfields. (Refer to Figure 1. Pie Chart)

Figure 1. Pie chart showing the number of topic samples within each subfield under the overarching field of neuroscience.

The distribution of distinct topics within each subfield was also assessed. Out of 199 total topics, *Cognitive Neuroscience* contains 82 topics, and *Cellular and Molecular Neuroscience* 51, representing the largest proportion of topic coverage. Subfields such as *Neurology* include 30 topics, *Endocrine and Autonomic Systems* 12, *Sensory Systems* 9, *Developmental Neuroscience* 7, *Behavioral Neuroscience* 5, and *Biological Psychiatry* 3. This demonstrates a wide variation in topic representation, with several subfields contributing very few topics relative to the more prominent subfields. (Refer to Figure 2. Line Chart)

Figure 2. Line chart showing how topics are distributed across subfields within the broader field of neuroscience

Finally, the total number of works associated with each topic was examined, totaling 15,382,667 works. Certain topics account for a disproportionately large number of works, including *Neuroscience and Neuropharmacology Research* (2,340,588 works), *EEG and Brain-Computer Interfaces* (1,102,656 works), and *Neural Dynamics and Brain Function* (802,956 works). Other mid-range topics include *Autism Spectrum Disorder Research* (763,329), *Neuropeptides and Animal Physiology* (614,832), *Visual Perception and Processing Mechanisms* (612,552), and *Functional Brain Connectivity Studies* (437,070). Conversely, topics such as *Axon Guidance and Neuronal Signaling* (50,270 works), *Hemispheric Dysfunction* (15,409), *Free Will and Agency* (17,010), and *Embodied and Extended Cognition* (10,485) show minimal representation. These quantitative findings illustrate significant variability in topic sample size, subfield representation, and research output within the broader field of neuroscience. (Refer to Figure 3. Bar graph)

Figure 3: Bar graph depicting the number of Works Count per Topic (children).

3.2 Qualitative Evaluation

The quantitative findings reveal notable imbalances in the distribution of topics and works across neuroscience subfields, which has critical implications for bibliometric analyses and field-level interpretation. *Cognitive Neuroscience* and *Cellular and Molecular Neuroscience* dominate both in topic count and associated works, whereas subfields such as *Behavioral Neuroscience*, *Biological Psychiatry*, and *Developmental Neuroscience* are consistently underrepresented.

These disparities indicate that smaller or emerging subfields may be systematically overlooked, limiting visibility and potentially biasing assessments derived from OpenAlex.

The distribution of works per topic further emphasizes this imbalance. *Neuroscience and Neuropharmacology Research* alone encompasses over 2.3 million works, far exceeding the majority of other topics. In contrast, *Axon Guidance and Neuronal Signaling* and *Hemispheric Dysfunction* contain only 50,270 and 15,409 works, respectively. This uneven distribution suggests that highly active research areas are heavily represented, while emerging or niche topics receive minimal attention. Such differences are likely to influence analyses that rely on quantitative metrics, including trend identification, productivity measures, or mapping of collaborations, as high-volume domains dominate aggregate statistics.

Structural imbalances are also apparent when considering topic allocation across subfields (refer to Figure 4. Sankey diagram). Subfields with high topic counts, such as *Cognitive Neuroscience* (82 topics) and *Cellular and Molecular Neuroscience* (51 topics), exhibit significant thematic fragmentation. In contrast, *Behavioral Neuroscience* (5 topics), *Biological Psychiatry* (3 topics), and *Developmental Neuroscience* (7 topics) remain sparsely populated. This pattern suggests that OpenAlex indexing favors areas of high publication activity while underrepresenting scientifically relevant but smaller subfields. Addressing these disparities could improve the accuracy and reliability of research classification, enhance discoverability for underrepresented domains, and strengthen the utility of the platform for bibliometric analyses and institutional assessments.

Figure 4: SankeyMATIC Graph depicting the number of topics per subfield.

3.3 Evaluation of indexing

I. Subfields

The evaluation of subfield indexing served as a critical step in assessing the accuracy and overall quality of OpenAlex’s classification system. To identify potential gaps in scope and conceptual representation, we examined each of the eight neuroscience subfields individually: *Behavioral Neuroscience*, *Biological Psychiatry*, *Cellular and Molecular Neuroscience*, *Cognitive Neuroscience*, *Developmental Neuroscience*, *Endocrine and Autonomic Systems*, *Neurology*, and *Sensory Systems*. Using a standardized chart, group members independently rated the quality of each subfield’s alignment with the broader field of *neuroscience* as *excellent*, *good*, or *okay*. These ratings were based on OpenAlex’s own definitions as well as the conceptual scope and thematic clarity of each subfield. Table 1 summarizes the collective evaluations and highlights the areas where the indexing structure demonstrated strong alignment as well as those where conceptual gaps or ambiguities were observed.

Okay = Broad: Indicates a general relationship that needs further clarification and refinement. Good = Moderately specific: The connection to the field is evident but could be made more precise. Excellent = Highly specific: The relationship is explicit and strongly supported by the provided definition.		
Field (parent) - Neuroscience		Scientific study of the nervous system
Subfields		Quality of relationship to field (parent) + justification
<i>Behavioral Neuroscience</i>	“field of scientific study”	Okay - Could likely justify creating a separate field for Neurobiology.
<i>Biological Psychiatry</i>	“approach to psychiatry that aims to understand mental disorder in terms of the biological function of the nervous system”	Good - Behavioural neuroscience and biological psychiatry may be merged, as they address related issues and both have relatively small sample sizes.
<i>Cellular and Molecular Neuroscience</i>	“branch of neuroscience”	Excellent
<i>Cognitive Neuroscience</i>	“scientific field concerned with cognition”	Excellent

<i>Developmental Neuroscience</i>	“scientific study of the nervous system”	Okay - Suffers ambiguity related to its definition. Some topics are indirectly connected to developmental neuroscience. Works under Anesthesia and Neurotoxicity Research do not belong in this field.
<i>Endocrine and Autonomic Systems</i>	“medical specialty”	Okay - Niche subfield. Both endocrine and autonomic systems relate to neuroscience, but should be treated as two distinctly different control systems of the body, which would be better represented under a subfield that encompasses both.
<i>Neurology</i>	“medical specialty dealing with disorders of the nervous system”	Excellent
<i>Sensory Systems</i>	“ability to interpret the surrounding environment using light in the visible spectrum”	Okay - Niche subfield. Definition only includes one of the four special senses identified.

Table 1: The accompanying table provides a granular breakdown of the manual indexing results by subfield, illustrating the reasoning behind each subfield's classification quality and clarifying the specific indicators that contribute to accuracy gaps. All definitions were taken from OpenAlex (Priem et al., 2022).

The results of this evaluation indicate that only 37% of the subfields demonstrated an *excellent* or highly specific alignment with the broader field of neuroscience. The remaining subfields were rated as either *good* or *okay*, suggesting varying degrees of conceptual clarity and specificity. Further analysis indicates that revising the current structure, either by merging certain subfields or introducing new ones, may enhance overall coherence. Notably, the subfields rated as *okay*, particularly *Behavioral Neuroscience* and *Endocrine and Autonomic Systems*, exhibited broad or ambiguous definitions that complicate accurate classification. Consequently, users may need to consult external resources to interpret these categories, highlighting the need for clearer scope definitions within the OpenAlex system.

According to Wikipedia (2025), *Behavioural Neuroscience*, also referred to as Biological Neuroscience or Biopsychology, examines “the biological and neural substrates underlying human experiences and behaviors.” This definition provides a clearer and more direct connection to the nervous system than the description currently offered in OpenAlex. However, despite its conceptual relevance, the subfield remains relatively small in topic distribution, making its status as a separate subfield difficult to justify. The interdisciplinary nature of *Behavioural*

Neuroscience further complicates its placement, especially when closely related areas, such as *Biological Psychiatry*, display overlapping thematic boundaries.

Biological Psychiatry is defined in Wikipedia (2025) as “an approach to psychiatry that aims to understand mental disorder in terms of the biological function of the nervous system.” This aligns with the OpenAlex description (see Table 1), which similarly emphasizes its neurological grounding. Yet, because *Biological Psychiatry* is situated primarily within psychiatry rather than neuroscience, its function as a distinct subfield within OpenAlex is limited. The overlap between behavioural, neurological, and psychiatric research creates persistent ambiguity regarding which topics appropriately belong within this category.

Developmental Neuroscience shows comparable issues. Although it focuses on psychological processes and neurological development, the subfield was rated as *okay* due to concerns about specificity and conceptual clarity (Wikipedia, 2025). Its small topic distribution raises questions about its scope, and some assigned topics, such as *Anesthesia or Neurotoxicity Research*, share only a weak conceptual relationship to the field. These inconsistencies suggest that structural adjustments may be required, a point that is further explored in the topic indexing results.

Across these subfields, the recurring issue is not relevance but fragmentation. *Behavioural Neuroscience*, *Biological Psychiatry*, and *Developmental Neuroscience* all address aspects of the biological basis of behaviour, yet each is treated as a discrete category despite substantial overlap. Given their shared focus, consolidating these smaller, conceptually adjacent subfields under a broader category such as *Neurobiology*, as illustrated in Figure 5, would provide clearer hierarchical structure. *Neurobiology* encompasses social, cognitive, and behavioural processes of the brain (Huang et al., 2023), offering a more coherent umbrella for these areas.

Overall, these observations highlight structural inconsistencies within the OpenAlex hierarchy, particularly among smaller subfields whose definitions and topic distributions lack precision. A more integrated approach may strengthen the system’s conceptual clarity and support more accurate indexing.

Figure 6: Proposed restructuring of existing subfields.

In the same vein, the subfields *Endocrine and Autonomic Systems* and *Sensory Systems* were both categorized as *okay*. Similar to the other examples, they suffer from ambiguity in their titles and definitions. In neuroscience, the endocrine and autonomic systems are typically treated as distinct interdisciplinary domains rather than a single combined category. For instance, Wikipedia (2025) defines the *Endocrine System* as “a messenger system in an organism comprising feedback loops of hormones that are released by internal glands directly into the circulatory system and that target and regulate distant organs.” While accurate, this definition offers limited clarity for users unfamiliar with its neurological relevance, making it difficult to understand how endocrine processes fit within the broader scope of neuroscience. As such, this subfield may be more effectively classified under a domain whose definition explicitly captures its connection to neural regulation while still acknowledging its role in systemic physiological control.

Alternatively, the subfield *Endocrine Systems* could be improved by incorporating narrower MeSH terms, such as *Chromaffin System* and *Neurosecretory Systems*. Integrating this structured vocabulary into OpenAlex would broaden conceptual coverage, reduce definitional ambiguity, and support more precise and consistent classification. Figure 5 illustrates that while OpenAlex partially mirrors standard neuroscience classifications, it omits several subfields and topics captured in MeSH, including *Neuroanatomy*, *Neurobiology*, and *Neurophysiology*. Unlike OpenAlex, which organizes works into broader fields, subfields, and topics, MeSH provides a carefully curated, hierarchical vocabulary, with broader topics gradually narrowing into specific concepts (e.g., *Neuroscience* → *Cognitive Neuroscience* → *Neuroendocrinology* → *Neuropharmacology*). This contrast highlights MeSH’s semantic precision and further emphasizes its potential value in enhancing topic coverage and clarity within OpenAlex, a point that is expanded upon in the recommendations section of this report.

Figure 5: Comparison of OpenAlex and MeSH hierarchies reveals that OpenAlex partially mirrors standard neuroscience classifications, but omits several subfields and topics (e.g., Neuroanatomy, Neurobiology, Neurophysiology).

The *Autonomic System* presents similar issues. Wikipedia (2025) defines it as a “division of the nervous system that operates internal organs, smooth muscle and glands,” highlighting important distinctions between the autonomic and endocrine regulatory functions. These differences, however, are not captured in the broad OpenAlex definition (see Table 1). This lack of definitional clarity undermines indexing accuracy and weakens information retrieval due to semantic shortcomings. While the *Endocrine* and *Autonomic Systems* are functionally intertwined, they would be better represented in separate subfields. The *Endocrine System*, which regulates homeostatic functions such as metabolism, reproduction, and feeding and drinking behaviour, aligns more closely with *Neuroendocrinology* (Wikipedia, 2025). Likewise, the *Autonomic System*, responsible for involuntary processes such as heartbeat, breathing, digestion, and blood pressure, corresponds more directly to *Neurophysiology* (Wikipedia, 2025). Given their distinct regulatory roles, separating them within OpenAlex would more accurately reflect the “aboutness” of works associated with each domain.

Since *Neurophysiology* emerged as a more appropriate alternative subfield, other niche subfields with narrow topic distributions may also be more suitably categorized there. Although *Sensory Systems* has a comparatively more detailed description, users may still need to consult external definitions to retrieve relevant material, which is suboptimal for indexing performance. Without accurate or comprehensive definitions, the risk of “indexing inaccuracies related to synonymy and homonymy” increases (Stankovic et al., 2023).

This semantic discrepancy arises in part because the current definition of *Sensory Systems* emphasizes vision as the primary sensory function, overlooking the full range of sensory modalities. According to Gadhi et al. (2023), sensation can be categorized into *General* and *Special senses*. *General senses* include touch, pain, temperature, proprioception, vibration, and pressure, while *Special senses* encompass vision, hearing, taste, and smell. Each of these senses directly involves nervous system functions and often requires neurological and physical examinations for accurate clinical assessment. Consequently, the *Sensory System* aligns more closely with *Neurophysiology*, which provides a more precise framework for understanding these diverse sensory functions. This illustrates that subfields with limited topic representation may benefit from hierarchical reassessment. The proposed restructuring, illustrated in Figure 6, presents a more coherent hierarchy between the subfields of *Endocrine and Autonomic Systems* and *Sensory Systems*, enhancing clarity and semantic specificity to improve indexing and information retrieval.

Figure 7: Proposed restructuring of existing subfields.

II. Topics

The manual indexing analysis was extended to evaluate the quality of topics and their associated works across the eight existing subfields. To ensure consistency and minimize potential biases, three independent coders analyzed the first 20 articles from the sample dataset. Prior to coding, the standard deviation of topic sample sizes across the eight neuroscience subfields was calculated to quantify the unevenness of topic representation in OpenAlex. A higher standard deviation indicates that certain subfields contain disproportionately large topic samples, as seen in the topic with 12 articles, while others have far fewer works. This imbalance may affect indexing accuracy and contribute to inconsistent representation across subfields.

For the sample analyzed, the standard deviation was 2.88, while the mean topic size was 5.5 works. Most topics contained only three to four works, approximately 2 to 2.5 works below the mean, whereas the topic with 12 works deviated 6.5 above the mean. The range of deviation across topics varied from 0.5 to 6.5, averaging 2.88. This indicates that the typical topic lies nearly three works from the mean, a notable difference considering that most sampled topics contained only four to six works.

Following the establishment of a standardized coding procedure, each coder was assigned a specific topic from each subfield (e.g., *Neuroscience and Neuropharmacology Research*). To ensure the analysis captured diversity, the topic with the largest works count was selected for manual indexing. Each article within the selected topic sample was evaluated and categorized as yes, no, maybe, or wrong subfield. Instances categorized as belonging to the wrong subfield were attributed to potential random sampling errors rather than misclassification by OpenAlex. The results of this evaluation are illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 8: Double bar graph of the manual indexing outcomes across subfields, illustrating how classification accuracy changed following reviewer reconciliation. The figure highlights variations in coding quality and the specific subfields where topic misclassification was most frequent.

The results of the manual indexing analysis indicate that the overall distribution of topic assignments was 56.52% categorized as *yes*, 26.26% as *no*, 10.86% as *maybe*, and 4.35% as *wrong subfield*. The largest topic sample, comprising 12 articles within *Neuroscience and Neuropharmacology Research*, represented a disproportionately large number of works, as previously noted (see Figure 3). This topic also exhibited the highest classification accuracy at 92%, a performance likely attributable to its broad coverage and the application of terminology aligned with widely recognized classification standards, such as MeSH subject headings. Furthermore, the topic's definitions were sufficiently precise to facilitate robust alignment between individual works and their assigned category. Comprehensive indexing results and justifications are detailed in Table 2.

Article	Result	Justification
Chemoarchitecture of glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP) and glutamine synthetase in the optic nerve of the monkey	Yes	Investigates how glutamine synthetase “metabolizes in the primate optic nerve,” further contributing to research in neuropharmacology.
Discovery of (R)-(2-Fluoro-4-(4-methoxyphenyl)ethynyl)phenyl (3-Hydroxypiperidin-1-yl)methanone (ML337), An mGlu3 Selective and CNS Penetrant Negative Allosteric Modulator (NAM)	Yes	Fits well under neuropharmacology, as the paper examines mGlu3, one of the least understood mGluR subtypes, and contributes to developing more useful pharmacological resources for psychiatric disorders.
Tau Transport From Cell to Cell	Yes	This cluster investigates the relevance of these mechanisms to neurological disorders, including Alzheimer’s disease (a tauopathy).
Choline Esters with Mydriatic and Cycloplegic Action	Yes	Paper access is closed; however, the abstract indicates that the study examines how drug corneal penetration depends on their physical properties (i.e., the correlation between these modifications and the ocular effects of autonomic drugs).
Anticonvulsant properties of peptide ACTH4?7Pro-Gly-Pro revealed during amygdaloid kindling and audiogenic epilepsy in rats	Yes	Fits well into neuropharmacology as the paper examines a drug’s effect on seizures.
The effect of quinolinic acid administered during pregnancy on the nigro-striatal complex of rat's offspring: ultrastructural investigation	Yes	The work examines elements related to both neuroscience and neuropharmacology, focusing on the effects of quinolinic acid on the nigro-striatal complex of rat offspring.
Purification of a benzodiazepine from bovine brain and detection of benzodiazepine-like immunoreactivity in human brain.	Yes	Examines various substances and their effects on brain function.
Evaluation of neonatal lesions of the ventral hippocampus as an animal model of schizophrenia	Maybe	Paper access is closed; however, based on the title, the study appears relevant to neuroscience and pharmacology, with mentions of the hippocampus and schizophrenia.

Effect of morphine on the potassium-induced change in the level of reduced pyridine nucleotides and cytochromes in brain slices	Yes	Paper access is closed; the title suggests strong relevance to neuroscience and pharmacology.
Intraventricular Interferon-α Stops Seizures in Rasmussen's Encephalitis: A Case Report	Yes	Investigates treatment of a neurological disease (epilepsy) using specific drugs, fitting within neuropharmacology.
Periodic psychosis recurring in association with menstrual cycle.	Yes	Discusses recurring psychosis in relation to the menstrual cycle, addressing neurotransmitter activity and psychiatric symptoms.
Neurotransmitters in the cerebral cortex	Yes	Direct and accurate classification, precisely covering core topics in both neuroscience and neuropharmacology.

Table 2: The accompanying table provides a breakdown of the manual indexing results for the topic Neuroscience and Neuropharmacology Research, illustrating the reasoning behind each article's classification quality.

Stankovic et al. (2023) observed that the hierarchical structure of knowledge systems is heavily influenced by the scope of concepts, with overly broad or overly narrow concepts disproportionately affecting their placement within the hierarchy. Broad concepts, they noted, are often better positioned higher in the hierarchy to accommodate the breadth of related topics (Stankovic et al., 2023). Applying this to OpenAlex, a topic such as Neuroscience and Neuropharmacology Research, particularly the neuropharmacology component, may be more appropriately treated as a subfield because it encompasses an extensive area of neuroscience focused on drug effects on the nervous system. Reclassifying it in this way could promote a more balanced distribution of topics by consolidating behavioral and molecular research under a clinical or drug-focused framework (Wikipedia, 2025).

Restructuring Neuroscience and Neuropharmacology Research may also necessitate reconsidering the status of Cellular and Molecular Neuroscience, potentially removing it as a separate subfield. Such a change could enhance classification accuracy, improve knowledge discoverability, and facilitate more precise topic mapping across neuroscience (Zafar & Haustein, 2025). A suggested hierarchical adjustment is illustrated in Figure 8.

Figure 9: Proposed restructuring of existing topic and article.

In contrast, smaller topics such as *Neurology and Historical Studies* and *Anesthesia and Neurotoxicity Research* received notably lower accuracy scores of 60% and 0%, respectively. These topics exhibit limited semantic cohesion between their combined identifiers, for instance, *Neurology and Historical Studies* focuses on the historical evolution of neurological studies, inherently excluding contemporary research on neurological disorders, brain localization, and the neuron doctrine. As a result, three of the five works in this topic were memorials or archival listings rather than substantive neurological research, demonstrating how the inclusion of *Historical Studies*, based on the current OpenAlex definition, leads to inaccurate retrieval outcomes.

Similarly, the dual representation of *Neurology*, as both a subfield and a combined topic, creates unnecessary repetition and hierarchical confusion. This pattern extends across other topics within different subfields. For example, under the *Neurology* subfield, *Auditory Disorders* appears as a combined topic, yet related research is also included under *Cognitive Science* in topics such as *Hearing Loss and Rehabilitation* and *Tactile and Sensory Interactions*, despite the existence of a distinct *Sensory Systems* subfield. Such overlapping and duplicative classifications complicate information retrieval and obscure clear hierarchical relationships.

The *Anesthesia and Neurotoxicity Research* topic further exemplifies classification issues. Although the articles address nervous system processes, most focus on either anesthesia or neurotoxicity individually, rather than both. Combining these narrowly defined concepts produces semantic inconsistencies and reduces relevance, highlighting limitations in automated or semi-automated topic assignment.

From a hierarchical perspective, these challenges mirror those observed in *Neuroscience* and *Neuropharmacology Research*, indicating broader structural issues in topic placement. For instance, *Neurology*, defined as the medical specialty concerned with diagnosing and treating nervous system conditions (Wikipedia, 2025), should function as a distinct subfield focused on neurological disorders. However, inconsistent topic assignments compromise precision and

retrieval accuracy. As Beghtol (2003) emphasizes, classification systems must clearly reflect their intended purpose in relation to information indexing (Zafar & Haustein, 2025). This case underscores the limitations of machine-derived classification in interdisciplinary domains such as neuroscience, where overlapping research areas demand nuanced hierarchical representation (Zafar & Haustein, 2025).

4. Recommendations

While OpenAlex provides transparent and accessible access to scholarly works, the evaluation of its classification system indicates inconsistencies in the categorization of works across subfields. To enhance visibility, coverage, and retrieval accuracy, several targeted recommendations are proposed. These recommendations are based on insights from the quantitative and qualitative analyses, as well as the manual indexing exercise, and are intended to enhance the accuracy, granularity, and overall usability of the OpenAlex classification system.

4.1 Expand Underrepresented Subfields to Increase Conceptual Coverage

The evaluation demonstrates that certain subfields, including *Behavioral Neuroscience*, *Biological Psychiatry*, and *Developmental Neuroscience*, contain very few topics and limited works coverage. Expanding these subfields by introducing additional topics that reflect established research streams would improve balance across the hierarchy. External controlled vocabularies, such as MeSH or the APA Thesaurus, could guide identification of missing or underrepresented concepts (Shiri, 2006; Hodge, 2000). Subfields containing fewer than ten topics should be reevaluated to determine whether their conceptual scope is artificially constrained. Broadening these subfields would reduce the dominance effects observed in *Cognitive* and *Cellular & Molecular Neuroscience*, improving the overall equity of topic distribution. Additionally, merging closely related niche subfields under a more encompassing subfield, such as *Neurobiology*, may better reflect their shared focus on the biological basis of behavior, thereby clarifying hierarchical relationships and improving findability. This approach aligns with prior scholarship emphasizing the role of structured vocabularies in enhancing discoverability and semantic clarity (Rafferty, 2001; Priem et al., 2022).

4.2 Enhance Granularity in High-density Subfields

High-density subfields, particularly *Cognitive Neuroscience* and *Cellular & Molecular Neuroscience*, contain disproportionately large numbers of works and topics, yet the current classifications often fail to capture the full diversity of research within these areas. Increasing granularity through the introduction of more specific topics, nested subtopics, or sub-categorizations based on methodology, population, or conceptual focus can better distinguish between distinct research streams. For instance, subtopics could separate studies using

neuroimaging from those using electrophysiology, or human-focused research from animal models, allowing for more precise classification. This approach reduces thematic clustering, enhances topic-level specificity, and improves discoverability for researchers seeking targeted literature. Enhancing granularity in these dense subfields complements the expansion of underrepresented subfields, collectively supporting a more balanced hierarchical structure and mitigating the dominance effects observed in current topic distributions. Such refinement is consistent with prior analyses of knowledge organization systems, which emphasize the benefits of detailed classification for improving information retrieval and precision in bibliometric databases (Shiri, 2006; Barrett & Lockspeer, 2025).

4.3 Integrate External Knowledge Organization Systems

The *Medical Subject Headings* (MeSH) database provides a controlled vocabulary and hierarchical, tree-like structure that can meaningfully inform and enhance OpenAlex's topic classification. Mapping OpenAlex subfields to MeSH descriptors allows for inclusion of narrower, related concepts, clarifies ambiguous definitions, and standardizes terminology across the database. MeSH organizes knowledge in a hierarchical manner, with broader topics gradually narrowing into smaller, more specific concepts. For example, detailed terms under *Endocrine Systems*, such as *Chromaffin System* and *Neurosecretory Systems*, can define topic boundaries more precisely and improve semantic accuracy. Linking OpenAlex topics to their equivalent MeSH descriptors also allows the system to capture synonymous or related terms, reducing ambiguity and improving consistency. Furthermore, MeSH's multilingual terms can expand international coverage, facilitating the retrieval of works across different languages and regions. Integrating these structured vocabularies addresses gaps in underrepresented areas such as *Neuroanatomy*, *Neurobiology*, and *Neurochemistry*, enhances indexing quality, supports interoperability with established taxonomies, and strengthens the reliability of both automated and manual classification processes (Hauptka et al., 2024; Priem et al., 2022).

4.4 Standardize Topic Definitions and Mapping Rules

Qualitative evaluation highlighted inconsistencies in topic descriptions and subfield assignments. Establishing standardized definitions for each topic, along with clear inclusion and exclusion criteria, can reduce ambiguity and improve accuracy. Clear rules for mapping topics to subfields, along with documented authoritative sources on how topics are created and updated, would improve both human and automated classification. This is especially important for interdisciplinary areas, where boundaries between topics are often unclear (Rafferty, 2001; Shiri, 2006). Standardized definitions would also support alignment with external vocabularies, improve the accuracy of algorithmic assignments, and make the system more transparent and user-friendly, ultimately facilitating reproducible and reliable bibliometric analyses (Barrett & Lockspeer, 2025; Thelwall & Jiang, 2025).

4.5 Rebalance Topic Assignment

A final recommendation concerns the rebalancing of OpenAlex's topic assignment algorithms. The concentration of works in dominant topics exposes limitations in OpenAlex's current automated assignment processes. Machine learning models frequently over-assign works to broad categories, misinterpret titles, abstracts, or key terms, and underrepresent emerging or interdisciplinary subfields. This results in uneven distribution and reduced visibility for smaller or niche research areas.

To mitigate these issues, algorithms should be adjusted to limit over-assignment to broad topics, using metrics such as Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) to better distinguish closely related topics. Limits can also be applied to prevent topics from becoming disproportionately large. Regular updates of algorithms using more balanced datasets, including underrepresented and emerging subfields, combined with human review and quality checks, would further improve accuracy. These measures would enhance the precision of topic assignments, ensure fair representation across all subfields, and strengthen the overall discoverability and reliability of research within OpenAlex (Priem et al., 2022; Thelwall & Jiang, 2025; Haupka et al., 2024).

5. Conclusion

This study provides a comprehensive evaluation of OpenAlex's classification system within the field of Neuroscience, combining quantitative, qualitative, and manual indexing analyses. The findings reveal substantial imbalances in topic and work distribution, with *Cognitive Neuroscience* and *Cellular & Molecular Neuroscience* dominating, while smaller subfields like *Behavioral Neuroscience*, *Biological Psychiatry*, and *Developmental Neuroscience* remain underrepresented. Structural and semantic inconsistencies, including overlapping topics, ambiguous subfield definitions, and uneven topic granularity, undermine indexing accuracy and limit discoverability for less prominent research areas. Manual indexing further shows that broader topics with precise definitions achieve higher classification accuracy, whereas narrowly defined or fragmented topics perform poorly, highlighting the influence of topic scope and hierarchical structure on automated classification effectiveness (Stankovic et al., 2023; Barrett & Lockspeiser, 2025).

Based on these insights, recommendations include expanding underrepresented subfields, increasing granularity in dense areas, integrating external vocabularies such as MeSH, standardizing topic definitions and mapping rules, and rebalancing algorithmic topic assignments. Implementing these strategies is expected to improve coverage, reduce structural bias, enhance classification accuracy, and strengthen the overall reliability and usability of OpenAlex. While the platform offers a valuable open-access alternative to proprietary databases, refinement of its classification system is necessary to ensure equitable representation and precise retrieval across the diverse landscape of neuroscience research.

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